

Effects of Variation Theory-Assisted Guided Inquiry-Based Instruction on Students' Conceptual Understanding and Task Value in Solid Geometry

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Abstract

Background: Solid geometry is a challenging topic for Ethiopian secondary students, often taught through traditional, teacher-centered methods that hinder conceptual understanding and motivation. Guided Inquiry-Based Instruction (GIBI) has shown promise, but its integration with Variation Theory (VGIBI) remains under-researched in this context.

Methods: A quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test design was used with 102 tenth-grade students in Debre Tabor City, Amhara Region, Ethiopia. Participants were assigned to three groups: EG1 (VGIBI), EG2 (GIBI alone), and CG (traditional teaching methods). Data were collected using a conceptual understanding test and a task value questionnaire. MANOVA and ANCOVA were applied to analyze differences in task value dimensions and conceptual understanding, controlling for pre-test scores.

Results: VGIBI significantly improved intrinsic value ($p < .001$) and attainment value ($p = .001$) compared to GIBI and traditional teaching methods, with no significant effect on utility value. Students in the VGIBI group also achieved significantly higher conceptual understanding post-test scores ($p < .001$), with the instructional method explaining 23.6% of the variance. Effect sizes were large for conceptual understanding improvement in the VGIBI group ($d = 1.26$). The findings suggest that VGIBI enhances both cognitive and motivational outcomes by making geometric concepts more discernible and engaging through structured variation. The lack of change in utility value indicates that perceived relevance may require longer-term or contextually explicit interventions.

Conclusion: VGIBI is an effective pedagogical approach for improving students' conceptual understanding and task value in solid geometry. It is recommended for adoption in Ethiopian mathematics classrooms and similar educational settings to support meaningful learning and motivation.

Keywords: Conceptual understanding; Guided inquiry-based instruction; Solid geometry; Task value; Variation theory

1. Introduction

Solid geometry is a cornerstone of secondary school mathematics. It covers three-dimensional shapes, spatial relationships, and geometric properties that are vital for critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills (Eurydice, 2022). Mastery of solid geometry equips students with tools for academic and career success. It also fosters competencies required in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields (OECD, 2018).

Ethiopian students, in particular, face challenges in grasping three-dimensional concepts and maintaining motivation, mostly attributed to traditional teaching methods (TTM) (Aziz & Kang, 2021). In the Ethiopian context, TTM is characterized by direct instruction, procedural demonstrations, rote memorization of formulas, and individual practice with textbook problems. While this method is efficient for curriculum coverage and knowledge transmission, studies indicate it often limits student engagement and hinders the development of deep conceptual understanding, leading to low achievement and negative attitudes toward geometry (Demssie & Yimam, 2019; Elastika et al., 2021; Istikomah et al., 2022). These issues are compounded by negative attitudes toward mathematics, as reflected in declining national assessment scores over the past decade (NEAEA, 2017).

Conceptual understanding (CU) of mathematical concepts, operations, and relationships is essential for modern citizens, enabling them to reason mathematically, grasp the rationale behind procedures, apply core concepts to unfamiliar contexts, articulate their understanding, and solve problems effectively across contexts (Nisa et al., 2020).

In particular, learning solid geometry with understanding significantly improves secondary students' overall mathematics achievement by enhancing their problem-solving skills, spatial reasoning, and confidence in handling complex mathematical problems, and addressing foundational weaknesses in Ethiopian mathematics education. However, rote memorization remains prevalent due to TTM, undermining Ethiopian secondary school students' ability to transfer knowledge effectively (Demssie & Yimam, 2019; Mekuria & Teketel, 2019). Additionally, without active engagement, students often struggle with spatial reasoning and complex problem-solving (Nisa et al., 2020).

Task value (TV), a key construct of Expectancy-Value Theory, also plays a significant role in mathematics education. TV comprises three dimensions: intrinsic value (interest in learning), attainment value (importance of success), and utility value (perceived relevance), which directly influence student engagement and achievement (Eccles et al., 2019; Shang et al., 2023). For instance, a student who enjoys exploring geometric concepts (intrinsic value) will likely believe performing well in geometry is essential for their present or future success (attainment value). If they also see geometry as relevant to their day-to-day life or future career aspirations (utility value), they are more inclined to stay motivated and excel in the subject. Such students typically invest more effort and persist through challenges, leading to improved academic performance (Jones & Hite, 2020).

Research findings also revealed that these TV dimensions are critical predictors of educational outcomes, such as test scores, grade point average, academic engagement, motivation, and course-taking intentions in STEM fields (Chirinos, 2017; Jiang et al., 2020; Tsao & Tung, 2022; Wang & Xue, 2022). Enhancing intrinsic and attainment values can motivate students to engage with challenging subjects like geometry, while utility value connects learning to real-world applications (Eccles et al., 2019; Rosenzweig et al., 2019).

These findings underscore the need for an innovative instructional method, such as Guided Inquiry-Based Instruction (GIBI), for Ethiopian secondary school students with mathematics achievement problems.

GIBI, grounded in constructivist principles, has emerged as an effective approach to improving secondary students' engagement (Joseph et al., 2022; Nisa & Astriani, 2022; Yewang, 2017); CU in solid geometry by involving them in active engagement and exploration with teachers' support (Jumantini et al., 2021; Kuster et al., 2018; Odupe & Opeisa, 2019); and their perceived TV dimensions and motivation (Hukriede, 2021; Richter et al., 2022). While GIBI has shown promise, its integration with Variation Theory amplifies its effects, particularly in addressing abstract concepts like solid geometry (Lo, 2012; Voon et al., 2020).

Marton's Variation learning Theory and GU's Teaching through Variation offer highly effective strategies for enhancing students' CU by presenting geometric concepts through multiple perspectives and systematically varying content using different patterns (i.e., separation, fusion, conceptual, and procedural) (GU et al., 2017; Handy, 2021; Kullberg et al., 2024; Lomibao & Ombay, 2017). Additionally, these theories enhance the students' solid geometry TV by making the subject more engaging, relevant, and enjoyable (Jing et al., 2017).

This study is theoretically framed by Expectancy-Value Theory and the Variation Theory. We hypothesize that while GIBI alone can foster engagement, the structured, theory-driven approach of VGIBI will more effectively enhance conceptual understanding by making critical geometric features discernible. This improved clarity and mastery are then theorized to positively influence students' interest in the subject (intrinsic value) and the personal importance they assign to success in it (attainment value).

Despite growing evidence supporting GIBI and Variation Theory, globally, no ample studies explore the effects of Variation Theory Assisted Guided Inquiry-Based Instruction (VGIBI) on secondary school students' CU and their perceived TV in solid geometry, particularly its effectiveness in Ethiopian classrooms remains scarce.

This study addressed this gap by evaluating the efficacy of VGIBI in enhancing grade ten students' CU and perceived TV dimensions in solid geometry in Debre Tabor City, Amhara region, Ethiopia. By comparing VGIBI with GIBI alone and TTM, the findings would provide practical insights for improving mathematics pedagogy and inform future curriculum development in Ethiopia and similar educational contexts globally. The following research questions were proposed for this study.

1. Are there significant differences in post-test TV dimension (intrinsic, attainment, utility values) among students taught using VGIBI, GIBI alone, and TTM?
2. Are there significant differences in CU post-test scores among the instructional groups after controlling for pre-test scores?
3. Does VGIBI significantly improve CU in solid geometry compared to GIBI alone and TTM?

2. Material and Methods

The study utilized a quasi-experimental design with a non-equivalent control group pre-test and post-test design to investigate the effects of VGIBI on grade ten students' CU and their perceived TV dimensions in solid geometry. The study included three groups: Experimental Group 1 (EG1), Experimental Group 2 (EG2), and Control Group (CG), each receiving four weeks with four periods per week. EG1 received instruction through VGIBI, EG2 was taught

using GIBI alone, and CG passed through TTM. Each group underwent a pre-test to establish baseline knowledge of solid geometry and perceived TV dimensions. Following the intervention implemented in the second semester of the 2023/2024 academic year, all groups completed a similar post-test with reshuffled items.

2.1 Participants

A multi-stage sampling method was used. Initially, of the four government secondary schools in Debre Tabor City, Ethiopia, three schools were purposively selected based on their infrastructure, average class size, and availability. Subsequently, three mathematics teachers, one from each school, were chosen as participants through purposive sampling, based on their educational level, teaching experience, and willingness to participate. Finally, three classes each from the teachers' intact classes were randomly selected and assigned to the EG1 (n=31), EG2 (n=39), and CG (n=32) groups. They contained a total of 102 students.

2.2 Instructional Materials

The intervention was designed to address the abstract nature of solid geometry through structured variation and active inquiry. Supplementary instructional materials were developed by the researcher using the Bybee (2014) 5E instructional model (Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, and Evaluate) and tailored for VGIBI. The manual included 16 lessons covering 16 different solid geometry sub-topics, models, and pictures of solid figures to aid in teaching.

To ensure instructional consistency and fidelity across the experimental groups, a structured teacher training program was implemented. Before implementation, two mathematics teachers who taught the experimental groups (EG1 and EG2) attended a five-day training program to validate the manual contents and to familiarize themselves with GIBI, focusing on how they would implement it in classroom settings. The training covered the principles of the 5E model, strategies for facilitating group inquiry, and developing guiding questions to stimulate student exploration without providing direct answers. Additionally, one teacher who instructed EG1 received a day of special training on conducting geometry activities designed using variation theory. This session focused on identifying 'critical features' of solid geometry concepts and designing 'variation patterns' (e.g., contrast, separation, generalization) to systematically highlight these features for students.

Following the training, EG1 and EG2 students were organized by their teachers into heterogeneous groups with four to five students. Then, EG1 received lessons that integrated variation theory principles into GIBI, focusing on highlighting critical features of solid geometry through systematic variation. EG2 followed standard GIBI, emphasizing guided exploration without structured variation, whereas CG relied on TTM, characterized by direct instruction and rote memorization in their natural seating arrangement. The intervention lasted four weeks, comprising 16 structured lessons delivered over four periods per week. During the intervention, the study group's students were unaware of the different teaching methods they were receiving to prevent treatment diffusion.

2.3 Implementation Procedures

Here is a sample lesson topic, "Volume of Pyramids," that shows how the intervention procedure varies across the teaching methods (GIBI, VGIBI, and TTM) in three study groups. The sample lesson was conducted in classrooms equipped with a chalkboard, physical models of pyramids and cubes, and student textbooks. Each lesson lasted 45 minutes.

The procedure of GIBI in EG2

Objective: Facilitate students' discovery of the volume formula through inquiry-based learning guided by the teacher.

Lesson Based on Bybee's 5E Model

Engagement (5 minutes): The teacher asks students to recall the volume formula of a prism and define a pyramid in their own words. Students discuss in groups and share their answers.

Exploration (15 minutes): Using a cube model divided into three congruent pyramids: The teacher prompts students to examine the congruence of nets of oblique right pyramids they have at hand and compare the volumes of the pyramids formed from their nets. [From the congress of the nests, students could conclude the equality of the volume of the pyramids]. Then, the teacher helps students form a cube by using the three pyramids and asks them to express the relationship between the volume of a pyramid and the cube they formed previously.

Explanation (10 minutes): The teacher noted that three identical oblique right pyramids form a cube whose base area and height are equal to one of the pyramids. Clarifies the derived formula ($\frac{1}{2} \times \text{base area} \times \text{height}$) and generalizes its application to all pyramids (right pyramids with different base shapes).

Elaboration (10 minutes): Students apply the formula to solve volume problems involving pyramids with different dimensions.

Evaluation (5 minutes): Students answer different questions to validate their understanding.

The procedure of VGIBI of EG1

Objectives: Facilitate students' discovery of the volume formula through inquiry-based learning guided by the teacher. Additionally, the GIBI approach can be extended by incorporating structured variations to deepen conceptual understanding.

Lesson Based on Bybee's 5E Model:

The first three stages (Engagement, Exploration, and Explanation) follow the same procedure as GIBI in EG2, except for the generalization of the formula application. However, during the Explanation stage, the teacher raises a probing question: "Does the derived formula work for all pyramids?" This encourages students to consider the formula's generalizability.

Elaboration with Variation Theory (15 minutes): Students complete the following group activities and share their findings with the class.

Activity 1: Object of Learning: Confirm the formula's validity for right pyramids with varying height positions.

Invariant: The base area and height of pyramids remain constant.

Variation: The position of the height foot relative to the base (center, edge, inside, or outside) is presented to students on the printed paper.

Activity 2: Object of Learning: Generalize the formula to pyramids with different base shapes.

Invariant: Height remains constant.

Variation: Bases differ (triangles, quadrilaterals, polygons) are presented to students on the printed paper.

Evaluation (5 minutes): The teacher assesses student understanding through open-ended questions and group discussions, focusing on their ability to apply and generalize the formula.

The procedure of TTM in CG

Objective: Deliver the volume formula of a pyramid using a teacher-centered approach.

Lesson Plan

Introduction (5 minutes): The teacher defines a pyramid, explains key features (e.g., height and base), and introduces the volume formula through direct instruction.

Worked Examples (10 minutes): The teacher demonstrates the calculation of the volume of two pyramids using the formula.

Student Practice (15 minutes): Students independently solve problems from their textbooks, while the teacher provides guidance as needed.

Lesson Wrap-Up (5 minutes): The teacher summarizes the key concepts, emphasizes the differences between right and oblique pyramids, and assigns homework.

2.4 Data Collection Tools

Quantitative data were collected using a questionnaire and a conceptual understanding test. The questionnaire assessed students' perceived TV dimensions (intrinsic, attainment, and utility values) in solid geometry before and after the intervention. It consisted of nine demographic questions and 12 items for TV dimensions were adapted from Doz et al. (2022) and Fiorella et al. (2021) using a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). Advisors and two lecturers from the Begemidir College of Teacher Education (BCTE) reviewed the questionnaire to ensure its face and content validity. Then, the Amharic version was piloted a month before the intervention with a sample of 39 grade ten students from Debre Tabor Secondary School (DTSS) who weren't part of the study. The questionnaire achieved a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.777, indicating good reliability (Pallant, 2016).

The conceptual understanding test was based on the Ethiopian Grade 10 mathematics curriculum (FDREMOE, 2023). Then, its face was validated by advisors, two secondary school mathematics teachers, and a BCTE mathematics lecturer. The test contains 12 two-tiered multiple-choice items with four alternatives, administered both before and after the intervention to assess students' understanding of concepts related to the surface area and volume of common solid figures such as prisms, cylinders, pyramids, cones, and spheres.

Finally, the test reliability was checked through piloting it with 38 grade 12 students of DTSS, who had completed the grade 10 mathematics curriculums. The test analysis results showed that the test items' difficulty ranged from 0.3 to 0.6, with an average value of 0.48, and their discrimination index ranged from 0.42 to 0.71, with an average value of 0.54, indicating the appropriateness of the test items. The calculated reliability coefficient using Kuder–Richardson formulas (K-R20) was .706, indicating an internal consistency of the test items (Roni et al., 2020). The CU test scored out of 12 points; students who got both the correct answer and justification for each question earned one point.

2.5 Data Analysis

2.5.1 Preliminary analysis

We performed preliminary analysis to ensure that all pre-test and post-test TV dimensions data for the study groups met all assumptions of multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA). The results revealed that all study groups' TV dimensions pre-test data have met MANOVA assumptions such as sample size (using descriptive statistics); multivariate normality and multivariate outliers (using Mahalanobis distance); Box's test of equality of covariance matrices; linearity (using scatterplots); Levene's tests for equality of error variances; and Multi-collinearity and singularity (using correlation matrix).

Moreover, MANOVA was used to examine the differences among the groups in TV dimensions in the pre-test data. The results show a significant difference among the study groups in their TV dimensions pre-test scores, indicating the variation of groups before the intervention. Additional Analyses also showed the tenability of all MANOVA assumptions for study groups' TV dimensions post-test scores.

Furthermore, we analyzed variance (ANOVA) to assess the study group's CU of solid geometry baseline knowledge before the intervention by ensuring that their CU pre-test scores (CUPreTS) data fulfill the Univariate normality and homogeneity of variance of ANOVA assumptions. The results showed a significant difference ($F(2, 101) = 9.735, p = .000$) between the groups in their CUPreTS, indicating the group's inequality before the

intervention. Additionally, we ensured the attainability of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) assumptions (i.e., normality, equality of error variances, Interaction effect, and linearity) for study groups' CU post-test scores (CUPostTS) data before executing it.

2.5.2 Main Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to summarize the post-test scores of students' TV dimensions and CU test scores. MANOVA was used to examine the differences among study groups in TV dimensions post-test scores. Additionally, ANCOVA was used to compare the differences among groups in CUPostTS while controlling for their CUPreTS differences. Finally, a paired sample t-test was performed to examine the study group's CU of solid geometry improvement due to the intervention. All these analyses were performed using SPSS version 24 software.

3. Results

3.1 Task Value Dimensions Post-Test Scores Differences

Table 1 provides the descriptive statistics of TV dimensions post-test scores. For Attainment Value, EG1 had a mean of 14.13 (SD = 1.80), EG2 had a mean of 13.28 (SD = 3.09), and CG had a mean of 11.84 (SD = 1.69). For Intrinsic value, EG1 scored a mean of 13.65 (SD = 1.87), EG2 scored a mean of 11.26 (SD = 2.71), and CG scored a mean of 12.31 (SD = 2.22). For the Utility value, EG1 had a mean of 13.23 (SD = 1.93), EG2 had a mean of 13.00 (SD = 2.24), and CG had a mean of 13.63 (SD = 2.47). These imply that EG1, which received VGIBI, showed higher scores in attainment and intrinsic values compared to the other groups. However, further analysis is needed to check whether these differences are statistically significant across the study groups.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of TV dimensions post-test scores

TV Dimensions	Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
AVPostTS	EG1	14.13	1.803	31
	EG2	13.28	3.086	39
	CG	11.84	1.687	32
	Total	13.09	2.502	102
IVPostTS	EG1	13.65	1.872	31
	EG2	11.26	2.712	39
	CG	12.31	2.221	32
	Total	12.31	2.509	102
UVPostTS	EG1	13.23	1.927	31
	EG2	13.00	2.236	39
	CG	13.63	2.472	32
	Total	13.26	2.220	102

Note: AVPostTS = Attainment Value Post-test Score; IVPostTS = Intrinsic Value Post-test Score; UVPostTS = Utility Value Post-test Score

MANOVA was conducted to examine the differences among the groups in the three TV dimensions (i.e., AVPostTS, IVPostTS, and UVPostTS). The univariate analysis shown in Table 2 indicated that the study groups significantly differ in their attainment value ($F(2, 99) = 7.65, p = .001, \eta^2 = .134$), and intrinsic value ($F(2, 99) = 9.08, p = .000, \eta^2 = .155$), but not on utility value ($F(2, 99) = .70, p = .499, \eta^2 = .014$). This implies that attainment and intrinsic values were significantly affected by the intervention, with the VGIBI (EG1) showing the highest scores. However, utility value did not differ significantly between the groups.

Table 2: MANOVA result of TV dimensions post-test scores

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	AVPostTS	84.606	2	42.303	7.648	.001	.134
	IVPostTS	98.553	2	49.277	9.078	.000	.155
	UVPostTS	6.934	2	3.467	.699	.499	.014
Intercept	AVPostTS	17284.999	1	17284.999	3124.936	.000	.969
	IVPostTS	15534.507	1	15534.507	2861.731	.000	.967
	UVPostTS	17813.830	1	17813.830	3592.381	.000	.973
Groups	AVPostTS	84.606	2	42.303	7.648	.001	.134
	IVPostTS	98.553	2	49.277	9.078	.000	.155
	UVPostTS	6.934	2	3.467	.699	.499	.014
Error	AVPostTS	547.600	99	5.531			
	IVPostTS	537.408	99	5.428			
	UVPostTS	490.919	99	4.959			
Total	AVPostTS	18105.000	102				
	IVPostTS	16102.000	102				
	UVPostTS	18445.000	102				
Corrected Total	AVPostTS	632.206	101				
	IVPostTS	635.961	101				
	UVPostTS	497.853	101				

3.2 Conceptual Understanding Post-Test Differences

Table 3 provides the means and standard deviations of the study groups' CUPostTS. EG1 had a mean of 4.97 (SD =2.04), EG2 had a mean of 2.62 (SD = 1.48), and CG had a mean of 2.53 (SD = 1.81), indicating that the groups' CU means differ after the intervention. However, further analysis is essential to check whether this difference is statistically significant.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of CUPostTS

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
EG1	30	4.97	2.042
EG2	37	2.62	1.479
CG	32	2.53	1.814
Total	99	3.30	2.072

A one-way between-groups ANCOVA was conducted to compare the effectiveness of the three different teaching methods (VGIBI, GIBI alone, and TTM) designed to enhance grade ten students' understanding of solid geometry concepts. Student's CUPreTS was used as the covariate in this analysis.

After adjusting for CUPreTS, a significant difference was found across study groups in their CUPostTS ($F(2, 95) = 14.677, p = .000, \eta^2 = .236$) (see Table 4). 23.6% of the variance in students' CUPostTS was explained by the teaching methods. There was a weak relationship between the CUPreTS and CUPostTS; only 10.7% of the variance in students' CUPostTS was explained by the covariate.

Table 4: ANCOVA result of CUPostTS

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	151.518	3	50.506	17.811	.000	.360
Intercept	275.838	1	275.838	97.273	.000	.506
CUPreTS	32.247	1	32.247	11.372	.001	.107
Groups	83.242	2	41.621	14.677	.000	.236
Error	269.391	95	2.836			
Total	1501.000	99				
Corrected Total	420.909	98				

3.3 Improvement in Conceptual Understanding of Solid Geometry

A paired samples t-test was conducted to examine the effect of the intervention on CU scores across the three study groups: EG1, who were taught by VGIBI, EG2, who received GIBI alone, and the CG, who received TTM.

Paired t-test results in Table 5 demonstrated significant improvements in CU scores within all study groups. EG1 showed a significant increase in CU of solid geometry mean scores from pre-test to post-test ($t(29) = 6.89, p = .000$), with a large effect size as measured by Cohen's ($d = 1.26$). Similarly, EG2 showed a significant increase in mean scores ($t(36) = 2.03, p = .050$), with a small effect size ($d = .334$). Surprisingly, the CG demonstrated a significant increase in mean scores from the pre-test to the post-test ($t(31) = 4.82, p = .000$), with a moderate effect size ($d = .85$). This shows that when compared with GIBI alone and TTM, VGIBI significantly improved grade ten students' understanding of solid geometry concepts.

Table 5: Paired samples t-test of CU

		Mean	Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Cohen's d
				Lower	Upper				
EG1	CUPostTS - CUPreTS	2.533	2.013	1.782	3.285	6.894	29	.000	1.258
EG2	CUPostTS - CUPreTS	.622	1.861	.001	1.242	2.032	36	.050	0.334
CG	CUPostTS - CUPreTS	1.563	1.831	.903	2.222	4.829	31	.000	0.853

4. Discussion

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of VGIBI on tenth-grade students' conceptual understanding and task value dimensions in solid geometry. The findings provide strong evidence for the integrated theoretical framework, demonstrating that VGIBI significantly enhances both cognitive and motivational outcomes compared to GIBI alone and TTM.

4.1 Effects on Task Value Dimensions

The MANOVA results showed significant differences in attainment and intrinsic values, with EG1 outperforming both EG2 and CG. This suggests that VGIBI was more effective at making students value success in geometry (attainment value) and find the tasks interesting (intrinsic value).

The significantly higher attainment value in EG1 suggests that by making geometric concepts more comprehensible through systematic variation, students began to see mastery of these tasks as more personally important and achievable. This aligns with the notion that perceived competence is a key driver of attainment value (Eccles et al., 2019). Besides, this finding is consistent with Marton's and GU's variation theories, which posit that learning is facilitated when students experience structured variation in critical aspects of the subject matter, allowing them to discern patterns and relationships that make the learning meaningful (Gu et al., 2017; Kullberg et al., 2024; Lo, 2012).

The notable difference in intrinsic value between EG1 and EG2 is particularly revealing. It indicates that integrating variation theory into the inquiry process made the content more engaging and the discovery process interesting. The structured variation likely reduced frustration and provided a clearer path to understanding, thereby increasing enjoyment. This finding supports the view of Jing et al. (2017) that variation theory enhances the inquiry process. In contrast, EG2, which received GIBI alone, did not show such substantial improvements, indicating that without the structured variation to guide the inquiry, the approach may have lacked the depth and clarity necessary to consistently stimulate student interest. This finding differs from Riegle-Crumb et al. (2019), who found a positive effect of GIBI in enhancing students' intrinsic value in mathematics.

Interestingly, the utility value did not show significant differences across the groups. This indicates that students' perceptions of the usefulness of solid geometry for their daily lives or future careers were not significantly influenced by a short-term instructional intervention. This is a critical finding, as it suggests that utility value may be more resilient to change and is likely shaped by broader, long-term factors such as societal messages, parental influence, and overall curriculum framing (Eccles et al., 2019). While GIBI and VGIBI changed how students feel about and understand geometry, altering their deeply held beliefs about its usefulness may require more explicit and sustained efforts, such as project-based learning with real-world problems and career-focused discussions. This finding partially contradicts Riegle-Crumb et al. (2019) and suggests the relationship between instructional method and utility value is complex and context-dependent.

4.2 Effects on Conceptual Understanding

The ANCOVA result revealed that the instructional method accounted for 23.6% of the variance in students' conceptual understanding post-test scores, with the VGIBI group (EG1) significantly outperforming both the GIBI (EG2) and TTM (CG) groups. This substantial improvement can be directly attributed to the core mechanism of Variation Theory. The VGIBI lessons were deliberately designed to present critical aspects of solid geometry (e.g., the relationship between a pyramid's volume and the position of its height) through systematic variation, while keeping other aspects invariant (e.g., base area and height).

This structured approach enabled students to discern patterns and relationships that are often obscured in traditional or even standard inquiry-based lessons (GU et al., 2017; Lo, 2012). The finding that EG1 and EG2 were statistically different underscores that the addition of Variation Theory provided a crucial element that standard GIBI lacked for this specific content. This aligns with previous research highlighting the benefits of integrating variation theory with constructivist methods (Baskoro, 2021; Voon et al., 2020).

However, EG2 students and CG students weren't statistically different in their CU of solid geometry concepts. This finding underscores the potential benefits of Variation Theory in

helping students to grasp geometric concepts (Lo, 2012). However, the finding contradicts Mensah-Wonkyi and Adu's (2016) findings that confirmed the benefits of GIBI in enhancing students' CU over TTM.

5. Conclusion

This study provides robust evidence for the effectiveness of Variation Theory-Assisted Guided Inquiry-Based Instruction (VGIBI) in enhancing both conceptual understanding and key motivational factors in learning solid geometry. The findings demonstrate that VGIBI significantly outperforms both guided inquiry alone and traditional methods in improving students' understanding, intrinsic interest, and the personal importance they assign to learning.

The study makes a significant theoretical contribution by successfully integrating Expectancy-Value Theory with Variation Theory. It demonstrates that a pedagogical approach designed to enhance cognitive discernment (via Variation Theory) directly fuels the motivational engines of intrinsic and attainment value (key components of Expectancy-Value Theory). This provides a powerful, integrated framework for understanding how teaching methods can simultaneously impact both learning and motivation.

For educators and curriculum developers in Ethiopia and similar contexts, this study validates VGIBI as a powerful, holistic pedagogical approach. The successful integration of Variation Theory and GIBI offers a structured yet flexible framework for making challenging mathematical concepts more accessible and engaging. By demonstrating that structured variation can make learning more meaningful, this study moves beyond a simple comparison of traditional versus inquiry methods. It provides a theory-driven mode for inquiry that is implemented in a way that is both effective and motivating, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Future efforts should focus on addressing the identified limitations and research questions, particularly in developing sustainable teacher training models and exploring methods to enhance students' perception of the utility of mathematics. By doing so, we can work towards fostering deeper, more meaningful, and more motivating learning experiences in mathematics classrooms worldwide.

6. Limitations and implications for future research

This study has limitations that also serve as avenues for future research. First, the intervention was relatively short (only four weeks), which may limit the long-term generalizability of the findings. A key question for future research is what might happen if VGIBI is used for a longer time would achievement and motivation improve more? A longitudinal study is needed to investigate the sustained and cumulative effects of VGIBI over a full academic year or more.

Second, the study was conducted in a specific cultural and educational context in Ethiopia. The centralized curriculum and traditional examination culture likely amplified the effect of VGIBI by providing a stark contrast to usual teaching practices. To use VGIBI elsewhere, adaptations would be needed to align with local curricula, assessment systems, and cultural norms around classroom discourse. Future cross-cultural research should examine the transferability of VGIBI to diverse educational settings.

Third, the lack of change in utility value points to the need for future studies to design and test interventions that specifically target this dimension. Future iterations of VGIBI could be

enhanced by explicitly integrating real-world projects, such as calculating the volume of local grain silos, designing model buildings, or connecting concepts to careers in architecture and engineering. This would test whether a direct utility intervention can shift these deeply held beliefs.

Finally, practical implications arise from the need for teacher training. The successful implementation of VGIBI requires professional development that goes beyond standard inquiry-based learning to include the principles of Variation Theory. **A critical question for scalability is how this program could be expanded to more schools, given the need for specialized teacher training. Future research should investigate the efficacy of different training models, such as train-the-trainer programs or online professional learning communities, to support the widespread adoption of this promising instructional strategy.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interest.

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